

Deliverable D1.2

Data management plan

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Log of changes

Date	Mvm	Who	Description
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17/07/2025	V0.1	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	First draft completed and sent for internal review
29/08/2025	V0.2	Martina Caloi (ELIXIR Hub) Louiza Kalokairinou (ELIXIR Hub)	Internal review completed. Sent to B1MGplus-MB for review
16/09/2025	V1.0	Ellie Younger (ELIXIR HUB)	Deliverable ready for submission

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1. Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan (hereinafter “the project DMP”) is a mandatory deliverable by the European Commission (EC) that has to be tailored to the specific project activities and which should document the relevant project repositories and how they are managed. The project DMP considers:

- B1MGplus project repository, accessible to project participants and external experts upon registration/approval.
- 1+MG (incl. B1MGplus) Stakeholders’ Portal repository, accessible to 1+MG implementation project Work Package Leaders (WPLs), 1+MG Working Group Leaders (WGLs) and Stakeholders. Access to this repository is managed by ELIXIR Hub.
- Examples of the relevant forms used across the project to gather personal data (contact details) are also part of this deliverable.

The project DMP is a live document that will be reviewed and updated periodically to ensure it remains up to date. The deliverable will have to be revisited, particularly in the case that relevant changes are introduced to the Grant Agreement, and in any case, at the end of each reporting period.

ELIXIR repositories used to store B1MGplus Project related data, including personal data (contact details), as well as the form used to collect personal data, are presented in this document.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

Outcome 1	Contributed
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Supporting the Genome EDIC WG and the 1+MG Member States on the establishment of the EDIC by carrying out the field work required to generate high quality landscape and scoping documents necessary for the compliance framework beyond the legal creation of an EDIC. These documents will drive EDIC to become operational and offer compliant access to health and genomic data, covering legal, policy, quality and security aspects of data provision.	1. A record of processing activities that captures the legitimacy of EDIC and the corresponding safeguards	Yes
	2. A number of documents that can be fed back to the GDI Pillar I and/or the EDIC for discussion and/or adoption to provide legal tools and policies to govern the operations for suitable and specific safeguards to ensure the protection of the rights and freedoms of the data subjects whose data are included in the EDIC for secondary use.	Yes
	3. A framework that can guide the implementation of national IT infrastructure to ensure the quality and the security of workflows, tools and platforms.	Yes
Outcome 2		Contributed
WP2 will analyse the EHDS Regulation and will seek close exchange with relevant projects and stakeholders to investigate the conditions for a participation in the HealthData@EU infrastructure, to give recommendations on the alignment of its policies, tools, security measures and IT framework with the requirements of the EHDS.	1. An analysis of the model how the EDIC could join the EHDS, its relationship with the various stakeholders and the conditions and opportunities of such participation	Yes
	2. Information on the practical consequences of the participation in the HealthData@EU infrastructure	Yes
	3. Engaging public health professionals, and policy makers, in the discussion of benefits and challenges of adopting genomics in healthcare systems for clinical practice and public health policies	Yes
	4. Documenting the implementation of genomic medicine practices in national healthcare systems	Yes
	5. Promoting the awareness, literacy level and education of citizens on genomic medicine across Europe.	Yes
Outcome 3		Contributed
WP3 will provide a framework of reference for genomics in healthcare that supports the decision making process, facilitating the definition of mid and long term targets and the path for genomics implementation, incorporating the	1. Mapping of gaps, challenges, unmet needs and solutions from the perspective of public health and healthcare professionals, healthcare systems and national genomic healthcare implementation programmes	Yes

feedback received from B1MG and the 1+MG experts.	2. Recommendations for the EDIC on the uptake and implementation of genomics for healthcare and public health	Yes
	3. A citizen's hub for dissemination of genomic medicine, promoting citizens and patients awareness, literacy and trust	
Outcome 4		Contributed
The project will map existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to whole genome sequencing and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare. Building on the collected best practices, and together with experts in the field, the project will develop decision trees to be tested in national settings to guide decision making related to genomics in healthcare. The long term impact of the work is the scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare to support future prioritisation in healthcare, policy makers and decisions on investment in genomic medicine.	1. Overview of literature and existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to WGS and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare	Yes
	2. Decision trees tested in national settings	Yes
	3. Scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare	Yes
Outcome 5		Contributed
Enhancing the 1+MG MLM for the implementation of genomics medicine in healthcare systems with updated domains and indicators, promoting its use and benchmarking by more healthcare systems. This will provide an homogeneous assessment framework that will foster the alignment of optimisation aims in healthcare systems across Europe, closing gaps, reducing asymmetries and ensuring a path towards equity of access to personalised medicine for all Europeans.	1. Updated 1+MG MLM incorporating novel dimensions aligned with emerging developments in genomic medicine	Yes
	2. Benchmarking of the MLM by healthcare systems across europe	Yes
Outcome 6		Contributed
Expand the 1+MG Framework to fully define the 1+MG minimal metadata model, data standards, ontologies and	1. Phenotype data model	Yes
	2. Genotype data model	Yes

quality criteria providing accessibility and maintenance, ensuring continuous alignment and support of 1+MG data use for research, innovation and policy making.	3. Terms of use/ELSI metadata	Yes
	4. Software quality indicators for components to be incorporated into the 1+MG journey.	Yes
	5. Data/metadata provenance models	Yes

3. Introduction

The B1MGplus project is a coordination and support action aiming to implement and sustain the 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG) initiative across Europe. During the lifetime of B1MGplus, personal data will be processed to coordinate the project, including names, institutional affiliations, email addresses, and other contact details of project participants, external experts and stakeholders, as well as information provided through event and repository registration forms (e.g., organisation, role in the project, areas of expertise). No genomic or health data will be processed during the life cycle of the project.

In this deliverable (the Project Data Management Plan) we provide an overview of the project data repositories:

- B1MGplus Project Repository ([section 4.1.1](#))
- Stakeholders' Portal repository ([section 4.1.2](#))

For each repository, we provide the following information:

- Introduction and background
- Structure
- Access level
- Registration and consent

In order to fully define each repository and the associated registration and consent forms (where applicable), we have considered:

- Applicable data protection regulations
- Lessons learnt from other ELIXIR Hub coordinated projects (i.e. ELIXIR-CONVERGE, ELIXIR-STEERS, GDI)

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Introduction and Background

ELIXIR makes use of the legal personality of an Intergovernmental Organisation, i.e. the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) (see <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/faqs>). ELIXIR also uses EMBL’s administrative and infrastructure service. More general information about EMBL’s legal status can be found here: https://www.embl.de/aboutus/administration/legal-services/legal_status/index.html

Among these services, ELIXIR uses the EMBL-EBI data repositories to store and share project related data with project participants. These repositories do not store research data, but project administrative data required to manage, monitor and control the project execution. ELIXIR intends to use these repositories also in relation to B1MGplus (hereinafter ELIXIR repositories) to monitor and control B1MGplus project administrative, legal, financial and technical aspects providing a collaborative workspace to generate project deliverables, milestones and manage internal and external communication activities. At the same time, it aims to foster collaboration across project participants. Access to the repositories is granted once the participants have been registered (by completing the registration form - see Annexes, Section 10.1) and verified (for the Stakeholders’ Portal repository - Google search of the person/host institution; for B1MGplus Project repository - checking their involvement in the project with the PI of the registrant’s host institution). Prior to completing the registration form, registrants are asked to read the privacy statement, linked at the top of the form.

4.1.1 B1MGplus Project Repository

To support the operation of the B1MGplus project, ELIXIR Hub, as Coordinator, has created a project repository in order to store and share relevant documents with project consortium members.

4.1.1.1 Project Repository Structure

The B1MGplus Project Repository Structure is presented in [Table 1](#).

Table 1. B1MGplus Project Repository Structure

Top Level Folders	Content
1. Project MASTER File	Master document with details from the project: contact lists, effort distribution, lists of deliverables & milestones, GANTT chart etc
	Project monitoring spreadsheet with details from the project: contact lists, effort distribution, GANTT chart etc. It contains

	details of all actions, events, deliverables and milestones, along with due dates and templates. It includes the email address of the partners' participants that are relevant for the monitoring and control activities: PIs, Deputies, administrative, financial and legal contacts.
2. Legal Documents	Legal documents pertaining to the project: Consortium Agreement, Grant Agreement, Description of Action, amendments, contracts etc
3. WPs	Working folders for the WPs
4. Deliverables & Milestones	Repository for project deliverables and milestones (templates, working drafts and submitted documents)
5. Project meetings, Events & TCs	Details of all project meetings and events (agendas, minutes slide presentations etc)
6. Periodic Reporting	Financial and periodic reports from all project partners
7. Guidance and Templates	Project handbook, containing guidance pertaining to all aspects of the project (processes, communications, management structure and responsibilities etc) Project templates: deliverables, milestones, agendas, minutes, slide presentations etc
8. Project Communications and Outreach Materials	Project branding & style guidelines, press releases, articles, presentations, newsletters etc
9. Grant Agreement Preparation	Working documents for the preparation of the grant agreement

4.1.1.2 Access

All project participants that have registered and consented to obtain edit access to the project repository hosted by EMBL-EBI and managed by the ELIXIR Project Management Office Team. External experts involved in the project by the WP leaders will obtain commenter access to the repository.

4.1.1.3 Registration

Registration form for project participants is presented in [section 10.1](#).

Registration form for external experts is presented in [section 10.2](#)

4.1.2 1+MG Stakeholders' Portal repository

To support the operation of the 1+MG initiative, ELIXIR Hub, as Coordinators of the B1MG project (Grant number 951724) created a Stakeholder repository, where Stakeholders could review mature outputs from the 1+MG implementation projects. The 1+MG Stakeholders repository will be maintained by the Coordinators of the B1MGplus project (see [section 4.2.2](#)) to ensure continuity and ease of access to information relevant to the B1MGplus project.

To build the repository, ELIXIR Hub made use of the same legal framework and repositories described in [section 4.1](#). To get access to the repository, stakeholders will have to register via the [B1MGplus website](#)¹ (or [GDI website](#)²) using the link to the form described in [section 10.3](#).

The B1MG project identified the need for the Stakeholders' Portal (intranet) and its data repository. The repository workflow was defined in B1MG deliverable D6.3 'Communication Strategy'³ and will be monitored by B1MGplus to ensure it remains fit for purpose.

4.1.2.1 Stakeholders' Portal Repository Structure

The structure of the 1+MG Stakeholders' Portal repository is presented in [Table 2](#).

Table 2. 1+MG Stakeholders Portal project repository structure

Top Level Folders	Content
Academics	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
Clinicians, medical specialists	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
Data & Quality Standards	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
Delivering Personalised Medicine cross-borders	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback

¹ <https://b1mgplus.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

² <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/newsletter/>

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/5018436>

ELSI	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback (WP2)
EU Joint Actions	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
Federated Secure Technical Infrastructure	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback (WP4)
Funders	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
HTA bodies	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
Industry (Diagnostic, pharmaceutical, ICT)	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
Infrastructures	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
Medicines authorities (EU, EMA & national level)	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
National Mirror Groups	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback (WP6)
National Policy, Decision makers	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
Patient Organisations	Documents for the stakeholders to review and provide feedback
Portal	Intranet files, Google Sites file.
Resources	General project resources to be shared with stakeholders
Stakeholders	Documents related to the Stakeholder Coordination Group

4.1.2.2 Access

Stakeholders who have registered, consented and been verified (Google search of host company/institution) get edit access to the Stakeholders' Portal repository hosted by EMBL-EBI and managed by the ELIXIR Project Management Office Team, as part of the B1MGplus project efforts.

4.1.2.3 Registration

Registration form for Stakeholders is presented in [section 10.3](#).

4.2 B1MGplus data protection management

As indicated under 4.1.1, ELIXIR uses EMBL's legal personality. EMBL is a distributed Intergovernmental Organisation. As such, the framework under which EMBL is operating provides certain exemptions from the applicability of national law, in order to allow for the efficient exercise of EMBL's official functions and to create a uniform legal environment within EMBL across all sites. Just like similar organisations, EMBL is not subject to GDPR. However, EMBL's legal framework, i.e. [Internal Policy 68 on General Data Protection](#), is adapted to the needs of international scientific research and reflects the principles of European data protection law, while remaining within the boundaries of EMBL's international legal status. More information about EMBL's data protection scheme can be found here <https://www.embl.org/info/data-protection/>).

4.2.1 Data protection officer

The data protection officer's details are provided in the [ELIXIR privacy statement](#)⁴ and copied below:

EMBL Data Protection Officer

Tel: +49 6221 387-0

Email: dpo@embl.org

EMBL Heidelberg, Meyerhofstraße 1, 69117 Heidelberg, Germany

B1MGPlus project participants will provide the details of their own data protection officer should they be legally required or wish to appoint one.

4.2.2 Personal Data Collection Management and oversight process

The project will be collecting personal data (contact data, i.e. full name, institutional email address and telephone number, personal email (if needed for access to the repository), institute affiliation, country (of employer institution), project role) in the following scenarios:

- During the registration as project participant - required to get access to the project repository ([see section 10.1](#)).
- When external experts are identified by the WP leaders - required to get access to the project repository ([see section 10.2](#)).
- When 1+MG Stakeholders register to get involved in the project- required to get access to the Stakeholders' repository. They will get access to the 1+MG Stakeholder repository only ([see section 10.3](#)).

⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/legal/privacy>

- When registering to attend face to face and virtual meetings: Project meetings (e.g. General Assembly), training events or workshops ([see section 10.4](#)).
 - Personal data collected: full name, institute affiliation, gender, dietary requirements, accessibility requirements.

The minimum set of information required for running the events is and will be collected. Data collected is kept on the ELIXIR repositories for the period of time requested by the EC in order to allow access to registries in case data needs to be audited.

4.3 B1MGplus surveys and meetings with experts

Surveys will be conducted by WP3 '1+MG Healthcare Implementation & Health Economics' during the course of the project for the purpose of delivering specific WP milestones and deliverables. Where these involve the collection of personal data, details will be added to this DMP document (see below).

WP3 Task 3.1 will organize online thematic meetings with experts on several topics, and will write reports on each of the topics. These meetings will be described in M3.2: Meetings with the network of health professionals on topics relevant for implementation of genomics in healthcare concluded. These meetings will also contribute to the final recommendations for healthcare implementation delivered in D3.5: Recommendations for the EDIC on implementation and sustainability of genomic medicine in healthcare systems, Month 36. Names and contact information of meeting participants will be collected for this purpose.

WP3 Task 3.2 will organize a webinar and tutorial on the application of the MLM for genomics in healthcare, D3.2: Tutorial and webinar for the genomics in healthcare maturity level model available, on M10. Registration will be required, and names and institutions from participants will be collected.

WpTask 3.3 will develop a survey for collection of information on national genomic programmes across Europe, collecting information on the respondents. This will contribute to the final recommendations for healthcare implementation delivered in D3.5: Recommendations for the EDIC on implementation and sustainability of genomic medicine in healthcare systems, Month 36.

WP3 task 3.5 held a first workshop on the health economic aspects of genomics in Romania, March 12-13, 2025. A meeting report on the output from the workshop is being finalised for **milestone M3.3: First meeting of health economics working group concluded**, due M09.

In preparation for the workshop, a baseline survey was conducted by WP3 task 3.5. The survey aimed to identify health economic resources and perspectives for scoping the work in task 3.5. People with knowledge of health economics and/or genomics were invited to

participate, including members of the 1+MG WG6 HEOR and selected external health economic experts. Personal information requested included name, country, affiliation, education, current position, and email for participants who consented to be re-contacted.

5. Conclusions

The repositories described here provide one of the key mechanisms to enable collaboration across all actors active in the project:

- B1MGplus Participants
- 1+MG Coordinating Group & WG leaders
- External experts
- Stakeholders

The forms used to collect personal data provide all the information on how ELIXIR processes personal data for the purpose of managing, monitoring and controlling the project execution and the delivery of the project's objectives and key results.

The project repositories have been established and are in use by all relevant actors.

The current DMP will be reviewed to ensure it continues to be fit for purpose and that any changes introduced in the repositories or in the process to handle personal data (contact details) are incorporated into the document.

6. Next steps

The project DMP will be reviewed before the mid term review or earlier if needed / requested. If any authorisations or ethics approvals related to the data processing are required, these will be obtained before the commencement of the relevant activities and described in the revised DMP.

7. Impact

The project repositories establish the foundation for a fruitful collaboration across WPs, with External Experts and Stakeholders.

10. Annexes

10.1 B1MGplus Participant registration form

Registration of participation in B1MGplus

Digital Europe Programme - 1+ Million Genomes: sustainability and uptake

The data you enter below will be used for the dissemination of information pertaining to the grant preparation and execution of the Digital Europe B1MGplus project (Grant number: 101194865).

Before filling in the form, please read our privacy statement [here](#).

Section 2 of 3

Participant Contact Details ✕ ⋮

The information provided below will be kept in a Google Sheet within the project folder so we can add you to our collaborative project repository, to the relevant distribution lists and to send physical documentation if required (e.g. certification of attendance at meetings). In case you can't provide some of the information requested at this point, or prefer not to, we will endeavour to explore other ways to ensure you can still engage and contribute to the project. Please contact us at grants@elixir-europe.org.

First name *

Short-answer text

Surname *

Short-answer text

Institution/ Organisation *

1. ELIXIR
2. EMBL-EBI
3. LNDS
4. INSA
5. Health-RI
6. NGC
7. CNAG
8. BSC
9. UU
10. INSERM
11. CNR
12. SLEX
13. ISCIII
14. BioData.pt
15. EKUT
16. KI
17. MSAE
18. BfArM
19. Sciensano
20. GRDI

21. UH
22. UL
23. UHEI
24. MU
25. HDIR
26. RBI
27. VUHSK
28. UiB
29. Vinnova
30. OOI

31. UNISR
32. SIB
33. MESR
34. CERTH
35. CRG
36. LBMC
37. IGG
38. Other

Position

Optional

Short-answer text

Country *

Short-answer text

Please provide us with your institutional contact details (email). Please do not provide personal contact details (e.g. gmail addresses) for this question. *

Your answer

If your institutional email address does not allow you to access Google Drive, please provide an alternative gmail address/email address that allows access (sharing of project documents will be done within Google Drive). Please contact us at grants@elixir-europe.org if access to Google Drive will be a problem.

You may also try using this link which may support you in making your institutional email address compatible with GDrive: <https://support.google.com/accounts/answer/176347?co=GENIE.Platform=Desktop&hl=en>

Your answer

Section 3 of 3

B1MGplus WPs and other Distribution Lists

Description (optional)

Which mailing lists would you like to subscribe to? *

- WP1 Project coordination and support to 1+MG initiative
- WP2 Genome EDIC establishment
- WP3 1+MG Healthcare Implementation & Health Economics
- WP4 1+MG Data requirements
- Administration
- Finance
- Legal

10.2 B1MGplus External Experts registration form

Section 1 of 3

B1MGplus (EC DIGITAL 101194865) External Expert Registration

B *I* U

The data you enter below will be used for the activities related to the execution of the Digital Europe B1MGplus project (EC Grant number: 101194865), including but not limited to management, coordination and communications activities related to the grant.

In accordance with the Grant Agreement, your data will be retained during the project and deleted when it has ended as soon as the retention period established by the EC is over.

If you would like to access, update or delete your personal data in the meantime, please contact us using grants@elixir-europe.org.

Before filling in this survey, please read our privacy statement [here](#).

As a B1MGplus External Expert, you will engage with the work being carried out in the different ^{*} Work Packages. Please indicate that you agree to keep project discussion and information confidential within the project and not to disclose them externally unless written permission is obtained by the project coordinator (b1mgplus-Coordination@elixir-europe.org)

Agree

⋮

Do you agree for your name, affiliation and email address to be used to create email distribution lists and other documentation (e.g. participant table in a Google Doc, PDF or Google Sheet accessible to consortium members) that will facilitate the coordination of this grant.

 Multiple choice ▾

Agree ✕

Disagree ✕

Add option or [Add "Other"](#)

 Required ⋮

Section 2 of 3

Participant Contact Details ✕ ⋮

The information below will be kept in a Google Sheet on the project folder so we can add you to our collaborative Google Drive, to the distribution lists that are relevant for you and to send you physical documentation if required (e.g. certification of attendance at meetings). In case you can't provide some of the information requested at this point, or prefer not to, we will endeavour to explore other ways to ensure you can still engage and contribute to the project. Please contact us at grants@elixir-europe.org

Name *

Short-answer text

.....

Surname *

Short-answer text

.....

Select your Organisation/Institution (among the ones taking part in B1MGplus), or provide details *

ELIXIR Hub

LNDS

INSA

HEALTH-RI

NGC

CNAG

BSC

UU

INSERM

CNR

SLEX

ISCIII

BioData.pt

EKUT

KI

MSAE

BfArM

Sciensano

UH

- UL
- UHEI
- MU
- HDIR
- RBI
- VUHSK
- UiB
- Vinnova
- OOI
- UNISR
- SIB

- MESR
- CERTH
- CRG
- LBMC
- IGG
- Other...

Position in your organisation

Short-answer text

.....

Organisation/Institution address. Note: This information (along with city, country and postcode details) will only be used if we need to send you original documents, e.g. certificate of attendance. If not provided now we will need to request it at a later stage.

Short-answer text
.....

Organisation/Institution Post Code

Short-answer text
.....

City

Short-answer text
.....

Country

Short-answer text
.....

Please provide us with your institutional contact details (email). Please **do not** provide personal contact details for this question (e.g. gmail addresses). *

Short-answer text
.....

If your institutional email address does not allow you to access Google Drive, please provide an alternative gmail address / email address that allows access (sharing of project documents will be done within GDrive). Please contact us at grants@elixir-europe.org if access to GDrive will be a problem.

Short-answer text
.....

Organisation/Institution Telephone number (for urgent communication - e.g. meeting/travel updates).

Short-answer text
.....

Section 3 of 3

B1MGplus External Experts

Description (optional)

Please indicate which B1MGplus Work Package (WP) you will engage with *

- WP1 Project coordination and support to 1+MG initiative
- WP2 Genome EDIC establishment
- WP3 1+MG Healthcare Implementation & Health Economics
- WP4 1+MG Data requirements

Please indicate whether you agree to be added to the B1MGplus-ExternalExperts@elixir-europe.org Group mailing list. *

- Agree
- Disagree

10.3 1+MG Stakeholders registration form

Section 1 of 3

Become a 1+MG/GDI/B1MG Stakeholder

B *I* U

This is the registration form to become a stakeholder of the 1+MG initiative via the B1MG/GDI Projects. We aim to create a vibrant community that will work together to improve the project outcomes. If you are part of any of the following groups, we want your feedback and opinion:

- Citizens and patient organisations
- Clinicians, medical specialists
- Academics
- Medicines authorities (EU/EMA and national level)
- HTA bodies
- Funders
- Industry (diagnostic, pharmaceutical, ICT)
- National policy/decision-makers
- Infrastructures
- EU Joint Actions

Once you've registered you will be granted access to the Stakeholder Portal to exchange ideas and connect with other stakeholders and Work Package leaders in the project. We will also send you details of project documents (Project Deliverables and Milestones) for review.

* The data you enter below will be used for the dissemination of information pertaining to the execution of the H2020 B1MG project (Grant number: 951724) or DEP GDI project (101081813). In accordance with the Grant Agreement, your data will be retained during the project and deleted when it has ended as soon as the retention period established by the EC is over. If you would like to access, update or delete your data in the meantime, please contact us using grants@elixir-europe.org. Should you have any data protection queries, please address these to the ELIXIR Grants team (b1mg-coordination@elixir-europe.org or gdi-coordination@elixir-europe.org) so that we may present them to the EMBL Data Protection Officer (DPO). You can find the ELIXIR Privacy Policy at <https://elixir-europe.org/legal/privacy#projects>

Please confirm that you have read and agree to the terms described above and wish to be added to the communication lists and your data to be stored and processed by ELIXIR. *

Yes

Do you agree for your name, affiliation and email address to be used to create email distribution lists and other documentation (e.g. participant table in a Google Doc, PDF or Google Sheet accessible to consortium members) that will facilitate the coordination of the grants. *

Agree

Disagree

Section 2 of 3

Participant Contact Details ✕ ⋮

The information below will be kept in a Google Sheet on the project folder so we can add you to our collaborative Google Drive, to the distribution lists that are relevant for you and to send you physical documentation if required (e.g. certification of attendance at meetings). In case you can't provide some of the information requested at this point, or prefer not to, we will endeavour to explore other ways to ensure you can still engage and contribute to the project. Please contact us at grants@elixir-europe.org

Name *

Short-answer text

Surname *

Short-answer text

Please provide the name of your Organisation/Institution *

Short-answer text

Position

Short-answer text

Organisation/Institution address. Note: This information (along with city, country and postcode details) will only be used if we need to send you original documents, e.g. certificate of attendance. If not provided now we will need to request it at a later stage.

Short-answer text

Organisation/Institution Post Code

Short-answer text

City

Short-answer text

Country

Short-answer text

Please provide us with your institutional contact details (email). Please do not provide personal contact details for this question (e.g. gmail addresses). *

Short-answer text

If your institutional email address does not allow you to access Google Drive, please provide an alternative gmail address/email address that allows access (sharing of project documents will be done within GDrive). Please contact us at grants@elixir-europe.org if access to GDrive will be a problem.

Short-answer text

Organisation/Institution Telephone number (for urgent communication - e.g. meeting/travel updates).

Short-answer text

Section 3 of 3

1+MG/GDI/B1MG Stakeholders

Description (optional)

Please indicate whether you agree to be added to the 1+MG/GDI/B1MG Stakeholder Forum mailing list *

Agree

Disagree

Please indicate which type of Stakeholder group you **mainly** identify as being part of *

- Patient organisations
- Clinicians, medical specialists
- Academics
- Medicines authorities (EU/EMA and national level)
- HTA bodies
- Funders
- Industry (Diagnostic, Pharmaceutical, ICT)
- National Policy/Decision Makers
- Infrastructures
- EU Joint Actions
- Other - please specify
- Other...

Please indicate other Stakeholder groups you are part of *

- Patient organisations
- Clinicians, medical specialists
- Academics
- Medicines authorities (EU/EMA and national level)
- HTA bodies
- Funders
- Industry (Diagnostic, Pharmaceutical, ICT)
- National Policy/Decision Makers
- Infrastructures
- EU Joint Actions
- Other - please specify
- Other...

10.4 B1MGplus event registration example

Profile information

Email

nikki.coutts@elixir-europe.org

First name *

Last name *

Event registration details

Prior to entering your details for registration, please read the [ELIXIR Events Privacy Statement](#) which includes information regarding the personal data we request, the external sub-processors we use to deliver events and how you may exercise your rights over your personal data submitted to ELIXIR.

B1MGplus partner that you are representing *

ELIXIR

Please indicate which WP(s) you represent *

- WP1 - Project coordination and support to 1+MG initiative
- WP2 - Genome EDIC establishment
- WP3 - 1+MG Healthcare Implementation & Health Economics
- WP4 - 1+MG Data requirements
- Other - external expert

If you have indicated 'Other', please state the initiative or partner project you are representing

Gender *

Please indicate if you will be attending, in-person or online, for each day

Tuesday 11th March *

Wednesday 12th March *

Details on how to claim for travel & subsistence have been sent to partners via a separate email.

External experts will be contacted regarding reimbursement rules following registration.

A working dinner is being organised at a restaurant
nearby the meeting venue on Tuesday, 11th March.

Participants will each need to pay and claim
reimbursement from their project budget (following
their institutional rules for subsistence claims).

Please let us know if you plan to attend. *

Dietary and Special Requirements

Your dietary and other special requirements are processed based on your consent according to the [ELIXIR Event Privacy Statement](#).

You are not obliged to provide any such data to us. However, without it, the ELIXIR Events team will not be able to facilitate your taking part in ELIXIR events by accommodating your dietary or other special needs. Specifically, please be aware that if you have any food allergies but you do not consent to processing of personal data with regards to dietary requirements, the ELIXIR Events team will not be able to ensure that catering at the event offers allergy-safe options.

I consent to the processing of data on my dietary requirements *

Yes
 No

Do you have any dietary requirements:

I have no dietary requirements
 Vegetarian
 Vegan
 Other

I consent to the processing of data on my special requirements *

Yes
 No

Do you have any special requirements?

Digital content at ELIXIR events

Occasionally, the ELIXIR Hub may record videos and/or take photographs to promote the event. By attending the event you consent to be video-recorded and/or photographed. You also consent to the further use of the video-recordings and photographs for promotional purposes, i.e. publication of this material on ELIXIR webpages (e.g. ELIXIR public website and intranet) and ELIXIR social media accounts. You may withdraw your consent at any time by emailing us at dataprotection@elixir-europe.org or by informing the event organisers at the reception desk on the day of the event. For further information on data protection and your respective rights, please consult with the [ELIXIR Events Privacy Statement](#).

Are you happy to be video-recorded and/or photographed at this event? *

Yes
 No

The [ELIXIR Code of Conduct](#) has been created to ensure that people at ELIXIR events can interact with each other in a respectful and safe environment. It provides ways you can voice your concern if you believe there has been a breach to this Code of Conduct. The ELIXIR Code of Conduct will be in place at this event.

